

A new polymeric sodium complex of vanillin : Synthesis, characterisation and antibacterial activity

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Abstract : The reaction of vanillin with 1.0% (w/v) aqueous NaOH solution to generate a new aqua and vanillin bridged polymeric sodium complex, $[\text{Na}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4(\text{vanillin})]_{2n}$ (1), is reported together with single crystal X-ray structure determination. The synthesized complex has also been characterized by elemental analyses, IR, ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectroscopy and thermal studies. The complex 1 crystallizes in an orthorhombic system, space group P_{na21} , with lattice parameters $a = 12.2469(3)$ Å, $b = 22.7142(5)$ Å, $c = 6.7897(2)$ Å, $\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 90^\circ$, which stabilizes in the solid state through strong non-covalent O...O intermolecular interactions to develop an extended three-dimensional rigid structure. The complex shows moderate inhibition activity against the growth of bacteria, *E. coli* and *B. subtilis*.

Keywords : Vanillin, sodium complex, polymeric structure, non-covalent interaction, antibacterial.

Introduction

Vanillin is an important compound used in the food industry, perfumery and cosmetics, animal-feed, manufacture of pharmaceutical, agrochemical products, as a synthetic intermediate, etc.¹⁻³. The bioactivity of vanillin^{2,3} and its non-linear optical properties^{4,5} are an area of growing interest in the recent years. However, the bioactivities are dependent on their mode of chelation with metal ions. These features include short intramolecular hydrogen bonds and packing configurations. Therefore, studies of the metal complexes of such ligands are important to explore potential new compounds. Vanillin can coordinate with many metal ions and some of its complexes have important material properties⁶⁻⁹.

The coordination chemistry of alkali metals finds tremendous applications in biology, chemistry¹⁰⁻¹² and biotechnology^{13,14} due to their interesting properties. In addition, recently, an increasing interest is focussed on formation of dinuclear, multinuclear and polymeric coordination compounds¹⁵⁻¹⁷ created by self-assembly of the components¹⁸⁻²¹. Though a few literatures on the coordination chemistry of vanillin are available^{9,22-27}, the re-

ports on vanillin chemistry of alkali metals are scanty^{10,26,27}. Therefore, in this paper, we report synthesis, spectroscopic characterisation and X-ray crystal structure of a new polymeric sodium complex of vanillin. The antibacterial activity of the complex has also been examined.

Experimental

General :

All solvents were distilled under N₂ prior to use. NaOH and vanillin were purchased from E. Merck, India. Elemental analyses were performed on a Perkin-Elmer 2400 elemental analyzer. IR spectra (4000–400 cm⁻¹) were recorded as thin film using NaCl cell on a Shimadzu IR Affinity-1 spectrophotometer. The ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded at room temperature in DMSO-*d*₆ solution on a Bruker DPX-300 spectrometer, and chemical shifts were reported relative to SiMe₄ as internal standards. Thermal analysis (TGA and DTA) of the complex was carried out in nitrogen atmosphere (100 cm³ min⁻¹) with a heating rate of 10 °C min⁻¹ up to 940 °C in a TA instrument; model STD 2960 using sintered-Al₂O₃ as a reference.

*Synthesis of $[Na_2(H_2O)_4(vanillin)]_{2n}$ (**1**) :*

In a 1.0% (w/v) NaOH (250 mmol, 30 mL) solution, the ligand vanillin (120 mmol, 0.182 g) was added in small instalments with constant stirring. The reaction was stirred for 3 h at 30 °C. The reaction mixture was then allowed to undergo slow evaporation at room temperature for three days when deep brown needle shaped crystalline product was obtained. Finally the compound was dried over silica gel in a desiccator.

Yield : 75%. Anal. Found (Calcd.) : C, 35.81 (35.5); H, 5.54 (5.92); IR data (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 1655 (s, ν_{CO}), 3403 (br, ν_{O-H}); 1H NMR (DMSO- d_6 , ppm) : δ 3.62 (s, OCH₃), 2.5 (s, μ -H₂O), 6.09 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, Ph), 6.90, 7.02 (2H, s, Ph), 9.19 (1H, s, CHO); ^{13}C NMR (DMSO- d_6 , ppm) : δ 54.2 (-OCH₃), 117–170 (Ph), 186 (CHO).

Vanillin [C₆H₃(CHO)(OCH₃)(OH)] : IR data (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 1667 (s, ν_{CO}), 3405 (br, ν_{O-H}), 1640 (ν_{H-O-H} , w); 1H NMR (DMSO- d_6 , ppm) : δ 4.0 (s, OCH₃), 5.9 (s, OH), 7.21, 7.42 (2H, d, J_{H-H} 8.4 Hz, Ph), 7.34 (1H, s, Ph), 9.62 (1H, s, CHO); ^{13}C NMR (DMSO- d_6 , ppm) : δ 56.1 (-OCH₃), 110–155 (Ph), 191.2 (CHO).

Single crystal X-ray diffraction :

Single crystals of the compounds were developed by slow evaporation of water at room temperature. The intensity data were collected on Bruker Smart-CCD diffractometer using Mo-K α radiation ($\lambda = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$). The structures were solved with SHELXS-97 and refined by full-matrix least squares on F^2 using SHELXL-97 computer program²⁸. Hydrogen atoms were idealized by using the riding models.

Antibacterial activity :

The bacteria were cultured in nutrient agar medium in

petri dishes and used as inoculums for the study. The components to be tested were dissolved in DMSO giving 0.5 and 1% solutions and filter paper discs of 5 mm diameter and 1 mm thickness soaked into them. These discs were placed on the previously seeded plates and incubated at 35 ± 2 °C for 24 h. The diameter (mm) of the inhibitory zone around each disc was measured after 24 h²⁹.

Results and discussion*Synthesis and characterisation :*

The reaction of vanillin with 1.0% (w/v) aqueous NaOH solution yields an aqua and vanillin bridged polymeric sodium complex, $[Na_2(H_2O)_4(vanillin)]_{2n}$ (**1**) (Scheme 1). The complex **1** thus prepared is microcrystalline solid, which is stable both in air and moisture. Elemental analyses of **1** were determined and the results matched well with the calculated values of the observed molecular composition. The IR spectrum of **1** shows characteristic ν_{OH} stretching at around 3403 cm^{-1} attributing the presence of -OH group. The $\nu(C=O)$ band of **1** at 1655 cm^{-1} is about 12 cm^{-1} lower than that of the free ligand ($\nu(C=O) = 1667 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) revealing the coordination of vanillin to metal through O-donor of -CHO group. The 1H NMR spectrum of **1** shows sharp singlets at 2.5, 3.62 and 9.19 ppm characteristic of -OH₂, -OCH₃ and -CHO groups and multiple resonances at δ 6.09, 6.90, 7.02 ppm characteristic of phenylic protons. The downfield shift of OH₂ protons, and the upfield shift of -OCH₃ and -CHO protons compared to free ligands [δ 1.25 (s, H₂O), 4.0 (s, OCH₃), 9.62 (s, CHO)] also substantiate the coordination of the ligand to metal through O-donor. The ^{13}C NMR spectrum of **1** exhibits characteristic signals at δ

Scheme 1. Synthesis of vanillin bridged polymeric sodium complex **1**.

54.2, 117–170 and 186 ppm for methoxy, phenylic and aldehydic carbons, respectively.

The complex **1** has also been structurally characterized by single crystal X-ray diffraction (Fig. 1, Table 1), which crystallizes in orthorhombic system, space group

P_{na21} with lattice parameters $a = 12.2469(3) \text{ \AA}$, $b = 22.7142(5) \text{ \AA}$, $c = 6.7897(2) \text{ \AA}$, $\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 90^\circ$. The sodium(I) coordination sphere is NaO_6 . Each Na^{I} lies on an inversion center and is defined by six oxygen from four different coordinated oxygen ligands in a distorted

Fig. 1. ORTEP drawing of the complex of $[\text{Na}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4(\text{vanillin})]_{2n}$ (**1**). Hydrogen atoms (except aqua ligands) are omitted for clarity.

Table 1. Summary of X-ray single crystal data and structure refinement parameters of **1**

Empirical formula	1 $\text{C}_8\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_7\text{Na}_2$
Crystal colour	Brown
Molecular mass	270.19
Temperature (K)	296
λ (Å)	0.71075
a (Å)	12.2469(3)
b (Å)	22.7142(5)
c (Å)	6.7897(2)
α (°)	90
β (°)	90
γ (°)	90
Crystal system	Orthorhombic
Space group	P_{na21}
Z	7
Volume (Å ³)	1888.75(8)
ρ (g cm ⁻³)	1.663
μ (mm ⁻¹)	0.208
$F(000)$	994
θ_{max} (°)	28.31
Reflections collected	4668
R (obs. data)	0.0504(3988)
$wR2$ (all data)	0.1406(4668)

octahedron. Phenolic hydroxyl group of the vanillin ligand is deprotonated and acts as tridentate bridging ligand. Methoxy and phenoxy oxygen of vanillin ligand is attached to one of the Na atoms in the form of $\eta^2\text{-O,O'}$ coordination whereas aldehydic oxygen is in the form of $\mu\text{-O}$ coordination with other Na atom together with coordinated aqua group with a $\text{Na}\cdots\text{Na}$ separation of 9.907 Å. All these coordination modes display a ladder-like arrangement of the 1-D Na^{I} complex. The Na–O bond lengths span the range 2.340(2) to 3.021(2) Å within the sodium octahedron (Table 2), which are similar to previously reported data²⁷. Within the same asymmetric unit, Na(1)–O(5) bond is the longest and Na(1)–O(3) is the shortest among all Na–O bonds (Table 2). The longer bond length of Na(1)–O(5) (3.021(2) Å) compared to other Na–O bonds indicates a weaker interaction in the former and is therefore likely to dissociate more easily. An interesting seven coordinated vanillin bridged polymeric potassium complex was also reported recently by Ceyhan *et al.*²⁶. In contrast to sodium complex in the present study, the potassium complex²⁶ showed significantly different coordination behaviour where each potassium ion in the polymeric structure is identical and seven-coordinated,

Table 2. Selected bond lengths (Å) and bond angles (°) of **1**

Bond lengths (Å)			
Na(1)-O(7)	2.408(3)	Na(1)-O(10)	2.386(3)
Na(1)-O(8)	2.414(3)	Na(1)-O(9)	2.380(4)
Na(1)-O(3)	2.340(2)	Na(1)-O(5)	3.021(2)
Na(2)-O(1)	2.401(1)	Na(2)-O(2)	2.403(1)
Na(2)-O(9)	2.599(4)	Na(2)-O(8)	2.449(3)
Na(2)-O(10)	2.596(3)	Na(2)-O(7)	2.459(3)
Bond angles (°)			
O(10)-Na(2)-O(7)	75.82(4)	O(10)-Na(1)-O(7)	80.84(12)
Na(2)-O(10)-Na(1)	98.15(11)	Na(2)-O(7)-Na(1)	101.41(11)
O(10)-Na(1)-O(5)	70.51(1)	O(7)-Na(1)-O(3)	88.67(8)
Na(1)-O(9)-Na(2)	98.47(12)	Na(1)-O(8)-Na(2)	101.81(12)
O(9)-Na(1)-O(8)	80.20(2)	O(9)-Na(2)-O(8)	75.38(13)
O(1)-Na(2)-O(2)	66.78(4)	Na(1)-O(3)-C(2)	125.77(5)
Na(2)-Na(1)-Na(2)	128.43(3)	O(7)-Na(1)-O(8)	91.54(5)
O(10)-Na(1)-O(8)	156.53(10)	O(10)-Na(2)-Na(1)	38.83(7)

bonded to two methoxy, two phenoxy and three aldehyde oxygen atoms from four vanillin molecules.

The complex **1** exhibits some interesting intermolecular interactions involving shorter distances than the sum of van der Waals radii (Fig. 2). The interactions between these molecules are presented by dotted lines and summarized in Table 3. The molecules are connected by strong intermolecular interactions between O atoms of methoxy, phenoxy and aldehydic group of vanillin and oxygen at-

Table 3. Significant intermolecular interactions in the complex **1**

D...A	D...A (Å)	D...A	D...A (Å)
O(6)...O(8) ⁱ	2.869(2)	O(6)...O(7) ⁱⁱ	2.889(1)
O(4)...O(7) ⁱⁱⁱ	2.765(4)	O(4)...O(8) ⁱⁱⁱ	2.793(1)
O(9)...O(4) ^{iv}	2.780(3)	O(9)...O(2) ^v	2.825(3)
O(10)...O(2) ^v	2.810(2)	O(10)...O(4) ⁱ	2.778(4)
Symmetry operators : (i) $\frac{1}{2}-x, \frac{1}{2}+y, -\frac{1}{2}+z$; (ii) $\frac{1}{2}-x, \frac{1}{2}+y, \frac{1}{2}+z$; (iii) $\frac{1}{2}+x, \frac{1}{2}-y, z$; (iv) $\frac{1}{2}-x, -\frac{1}{2}+y, -\frac{1}{2}+z$; (v) $-\frac{1}{2}+x, -\frac{1}{2}-y, z$.			

oms of coordinated water molecules of other asymmetric unit [O(6)...O(8) 2.869(2); O(6)...O(7) 2.889(1); O(4)...O(7) 2.765(4); O(4)...O(8) 2.793(1); O(9)...O(4) 2.780(3); O(9)...O(2) 2.825(3); O(10)...O(2) 2.810(2); O(10)...O(4) 2.778(4)]. These results demonstrate the extended three dimensional network structure as shown in Fig. 3. However, the polymeric structure loses the coordinated water molecule on heating during 100–135 °C as indicated by thermal studies.

Antibacterial activity :

The ligand vanillin and its sodium complex **1** were tested for the *in vitro* growth inhibitory activity against the bacteria *E. coli* and *B. subtilis* by using the disc diffusion method³⁰. Ampicillin was used as a standard. From the results (Table 4), it was observed that the Na-vanillin complex was more toxic than its parent ligand and the

Fig. 2. Intermolecular short contacts in **1**. The atoms involved in short contact (only a few selective interactions) from surrounding molecules have been designated by dotted lines.

Fig. 3. A view of the part of the polymeric structure along crystallographic 'a' axis formed by vanillin ligand, water and sodium ions.

Table 4. Antibacterial activity of Na-vanillin complex

Test components	Zone of inhibition (mm)			
	<i>E. coli</i>		<i>B. subtilis</i>	
	0.5%	1%	0.5%	1%
Ligand, vanillin	6	9	5	8
Na-Vanillin complex	12	18	10	13
Ampicillin	25	25	20	20

toxicity increased with increase in concentration of the solution of the test components. However, the moderate activity was observed for the test components compared to the standard ampicillin.

Conclusions

A new aqua and vanillin bridged polymeric sodium complex, $[\text{Na}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4(\text{vanillin})]_{2n}$ (**1**), was synthesized and characterized. The complex was also structurally characterized by single crystal X-ray diffraction, which stabilizes in the solid state through non-covalent $\text{O}\cdots\text{O}$ intermolecular interactions to develop an extended three-dimensional network structure. The complex showed

moderate inhibition activity against the micro organisms *E. coli* and *B. subtilis* compared to the standard ampicillin.

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Supplementary data

CCDC 887654 contains the supplementary crystallographic data of **1**. These data can be obtained free of charge via <http://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/conts/retrieving.html>, or from the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre, 12 Union Road, Cambridge CB2 1EZ, UK; Fax : (+44) 1223-336-033; E-mail : deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk.

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